

ARTISTIC INTERPRETATION OF THE IMAGE OF EMIR TIMUR IN UZBEK NOVEL STUDIES

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Abstract: In this article it has been researched about the specific features and laws of historical novels' genres. Furthermore, the progression of modern uzbek literature, particularly, principles of the emergence of Amir Temur's image in the work of poet and translator Muhammad Ali "The Great Empire" has been analyzed.

Keywords: fictional and poetic expression, imagination, impression, image human consciousness, spiritual world, philosophy of socio-political life, art of diction, the cultural life of the period, complex and controversial.

ЎЗБЕК РОМАНЧИЛИГИДА АМИР ТЕМУР ОБРАЗИНИНГ БАДИИЙ ТАЛҚИНИ.

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Аннотация: Мазкур мақолада тарихий роман жанрининг ўзига хос қонуният ва хусусиятлари тадқиқ қилинади. Шунингдек замонавий ўзбек романчилигининг ютуқлари, жумладан шоир ва таржимон Мухаммад Алининг "Улуғ салтанат" асарида амир Темур образининг гадаланиши тамойиллари таҳлилга тортилади.

Калит сўзлар: бадиий-поэтик ифода, тасаввур, таассурот, қиёфа, башарият онги, руҳий олам, ижтимоий-сиёсий ҳаёт фалсафаси, сўз санъати, давр маданият ҳаёти, мураккаб ва зиддиятли.

ХУДОЖЕСТВЕННОЕ ТОЛКОВАНИЕ ОБРАЗА ЭМИРА ТИМУРА В УЗБЕКСКОЙ РОМАНИСТИКЕ.

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Аннотация: В данной статье изучаются своеобразные закономерности и особенности жанра исторического романа. Также подвергается к анализу достижения современной узбекской романистики, в частности принципы формирования образа Эмира Тимура в произведении поэта и писателя Мухаммада Али "Великая империя".

Ключевые слова: художественно-поэтическая интерпретация, воображение, впечатление, облик, сознание человечества, духовный мир, социально-политическая философия жизни, искусство слова, культурная жизнь эпохи, сложный и противоречивый.

The novel is conditioned by the need for a comparative understanding of man and the world, the transfer of derivatives into artistic and poetic expression. This genre, sometimes riddled with historical problems, reflects the increasingly globalizing, intensifying pace of life and the character of our contemporary. Indeed, the novel "The Universe in miniature" (by V.G.Belinsky) and the "Reduced Universe" (by Saltykov-Shchedrin). For him, it is not the volume and magnitude of the period that is important, but the volume of content, the breadth and depth of the poetic scope.

The philosophy of literature, reinterpretation of the past, reality and the supernatural are intertwined in modern Uzbek novel studies. Fiction, as Chulpan put it, is "the story of the sensual heart." This interpretation is much deeper and more abstract than we think. Since the image of a historical person is a collection of facts and events of the past, a collection of past events, the history of the art world is even more extensive and incomparable. He understands that feelings arising in the human heart pass and flow over a certain period and distance, and that this flow is registered through feelings. Man, as long as humanity is alive, this stream is eternal. The secrets of the current are felt in those worlds that are unfamiliar to us, to one degree or another. Tafhul-Mahfuz, mentioned in the "Holy Quran", is sealed on an indelible tablet. But in our odic thinking, it seems that the pain and suffering of the sensual heart in the bright Universe are absorbed by the trembling of the soul to existence, and if necessary, to non-existence, and disappear without a trace. This trace-free, but sensual loss is excluded in a certain case of art. The art of the word, including art, that is, literature, encourages a person to ensure that feelings, imagination and impressions generated by the ongoing processes are concentrated inherited into the present and future, sealing the word, the word. The creation of an artistic

work is the leaving of a trace, a trace of the time to which it belongs. In lexical terms, the meaning of the word "work" is also a SIGN.

Literature, being a poetic art, naturally has to use its main weapon in this process-the word. It seals and reflects the sensual soul vibrations in itself.

A word in a genuine work of art, that is, when the word art – that is, literature – is enchanted, restored. The word itself, the various human states recreated through it -landscapes, relationships, dialogues-conflicts make it possible for such a peculiar meaning to arise that such a complex of meanings, depth and elevation make it narrow for literary studies and create the need for a new direction (scientific school) – the philosophy of literature. And the magic of the word is its specific area.

The image of our contemporaries is doomed to be observed from different angles. The birth of epic novels such as "The Great Emir of Turan or the Mind and the Sword" (Nurali Kabul) "The Great Empire" (Muhammad Ali), created on the basis of a deep understanding of history, is the fruit of national thinking. "The Great Empire" and "The Great Emir of Turan or the mind and the Sword" are close to folk heroic epics, great historical figures, generals in the beauty of the plot, the reflection of the epic scale; the destinies of many countries and peoples, the history of interethnic wars, pictures of the cultural life of the nation through the image of Amir Temur, striving to create a centralized state, are harmoniously combined with the style of historical and memoir works. The artistic content of the novel-tetralogy is a lyric-romantic understanding of the meaning of the sublime human life, the desire to improve certain criteria for its evaluation.

The most important aspect defining the poetics of the historical novel is its artistic and aesthetic impact on the spirituality of man and society, on the minds and hearts of people. As it is known, a national novel, a historical novel figuratively conveys our ideals. The novel expresses the influence of the historical process on consciousness, thinking, and the spiritual spiritual world of mankind.

The intensity of the period of independence was first reflected in the poetic thinking of the writer, and then acquired materiality as a novel. In this regard, it becomes obvious that a broad and in-depth study of the content, character, and direction of expression of writing national historical novels requires the search for a new direction of poetic thinking related to the problems of national historical novel art. The reason is that along with spiritual beauty, spiritual height, the Novel acquires a symbolic-figurative and sarcastic-satirical nature through the artistic and poetic expression of "modern" forms of denial of the human psyche and desires in conditions of

change, as it is observed in the epics of Nurali Kabul. No novel can be correctly and comprehensively interpreted without understanding the scale and expressiveness of the writer's poetic thinking. In the novel, the solution of all problems is determined through the perception of problems and the nature of their bearer, which the writer harmoniously places in the philosophical and aesthetic concept. Consequently, the theory of poetic scale also follows from the practice of the novel. Various discussions are underway in this direction. It is noteworthy that the debates were organized on the topic "Prose: today and tomorrow", held as part of a literary conversation.¹ During the conversation, literary critic N. Rakhimzhonov, using the example of the novels of modern writers: Muhammad Ali, Kh.Dustmukhammad, A. Dilmurod, E.Azam, emphasizes that in the novels of the period of independence, man and society are expressed from the point of view of new poetic thinking, and the content of artistic generalizations is becoming more diverse. And literary critic K.Yuldashev, using the example of the works of Nasirs of the period of independence O.Mukhtar, Nurali Kabul, U.Hamdani, N.Eshonkul, T.Rustam, M.Salam, A.Yuldash, I.Sultan, L.Burikhan in his written speech, highlights the following features that characterize the fact that modern Uzbek novels do not fit into the usual stereotypes:

a) Fiction, in particular the novel, becomes an expression of the spiritual and spiritual needs of the creator. The fact that situations that disturb the creative soul and do not give rest to its imagination turn into expression, into an image, is a sign that the focus of the artistic image is changing, the aesthetic approach is becoming healthier.

b) Increased attention to expressing in a unique and attractive way that the human personality is the cause and driving force of the process.

c) Each work turns into an aesthetic phenomenon that has its own figurative appearance.

The above classification is conditional. In this, the scientist compares the literature of repression period, based on the flow of "Socialist realism", and completely denying his literature of the period of independence. After all, if we compare world literature, then beautiful artistic expressions have always been an expression of the writer's spiritual and spiritual needs. Conversely, the original artistic text will never be able to come to the surface if the creator cannot transfer into the image those thoughts and feelings that disturb his soul and do not give rest to his imagination.

¹ Literature and art of Uzbekistan. November 6, 2015

Alas, for a quarter of a century, the history and principles of perception of human relations have completely changed. Artistic truth prevails over the philosophy of socio-political life and occupies a position approved by Aristotle. Today, the character has become objectively expressed as a living person with his everyday fantasies and behavior, and not as a confirmation of reality, as is observed in most novels of the XX century. At the same time, it became poetically perceived that the nature of an individual is a more complex state than social reality, and it is important to understand and interpret it.

Under the influence of the severity of the era, the need to show the spiritual and intellectual world, the world of feelings of people who are striving not to lose their national image, increased. Literary heroes who carry the mission of being a role model and guiding the reader, but deprived of their own personal life, human feelings and experiences, were also denied in the literary work. It was felt that this brought into the artistic prose the image of ordinary people living next to the inadequate bustle of everyday life. A wrestler, a gentleman, a carpenter, a shepherd, a peasant, a watchman, a farrosha, even who came from the village to the city and failed to take any social position, but who sought to find his place among people, realizing himself to be the bearer of the spirit of the nation, according to the observations of Professor K. Yuldashev, increasingly paid attention to the image of *"Heroes who did not become heroes."*

In modern Uzbek historical novels, the philosophy of history and literature, reinterpretation of the past, a combination of reality and the supernatural are important. The image of our contemporary is observed from different angles. The birth of epic novels such as *"The Great Empire"* Muhammad Ali, created on the basis of a deep understanding of history, is the fruit of national thinking. According to the wit of the storyline, the reflection of the epic history, *"The Great Empire"* is close to folk heroic epics, in the style of historical and memoir works, in the depiction of great historical figures, the destinies of many countries and peoples, the history of internecine wars, in the perception of the landscapes of the cultural life of the era through the image and personality of the great Amir Temur, who sought to create a centralized state. The artistic content of the novel-tetralogy consists in a lyric-romantic understanding of the meaning and meaning of the life of a glorious man and the desire to formulate certain criteria for his assessment.

According to literary critic Damin Turaev, "In this book of the epic novel, Muhammad Ali connected many heroes on a vast territory, in time and

space, the fate of Sahibkiran with the fate of the Empire, showed with what dedication, labor, heroism the Empire of Turan was built."² These thoughts of the critic are characterized by the fact that the Timurid era is extremely widely described in the epic novel, and the poetic scale of that time is historical in essence. After all, if the third book of the tetralogy describes an internal rebellion caused by the arrogance of Amir Timur's third son, Miron Shah Mirzo, who rebelled against his enemy and led to this resistance, and the actions of the perpetrators, then in this book we see that the son, like other perpetrators, was punished and conscious repentance, and also, the fate of the perpetrators were shown with exceptional skill.

The intensive display of time in the artistic evolution of the writer's creative idea even more clearly shows the reality happening around Sahibkiran, based on the phenomena of time and space. That is, the manner of linking storylines, the ability to skillfully apply the components of the composition indicate in this regard that the creative person managed to achieve the goal set for him: "Since, the maid's child!.. – he said to himself in anger... He never said this about the children he saw from his concubines, the first time he came out of his mouth. But these words were powerless to spread his goose."³ In the above passage, Timur's furious reasoning about his child Miron Shah, seen from a concubine, makes the reader think. And the letter from Ahi Jabbar was proof of the rebellion that Miron Shah had shown his father. In addition, the writer used the dialogical speech between Sultan Hussein Mirzo and Khalil Sultan in the fourth book of the tetralogy to indicate that Sahibkiran had reached the end of his life. In the tetralogy, the plot of the work and the problem of the pronotope give the impression that the last trip to China may occur in winter.

Scientific and theoretical research of the historical work "The Great Empire", which is the product of many years of creative work of Muhammad Ali, The genesis of tetralogy in the world and Russian literary and aesthetic thought manifests itself in different periods in different ways. However, in Uzbek literature it is considered that the emergence and development of historical tetralogy is associated with the work of Muhammad Ali. The key to the further development of poetic skill in creating a historical novel-tetralogy to a certain extent are the heroic epics in which Timur took part.

² Turaev D. Uzbek tetralogy. - Tashkent: Akademnashr. 2017. – p. 98.

³ Muhammad Ali. Shorukh Mirzo. Volume 4. - Tashkent: Navruz. 2019. - p. 127.

In European literature, the historical tetralogy unfolds in chronological order, all its characters are united in one center. Muhammad Ali in the image of Sahibkiran also brings the image of Timur to the central place in all realities, demonstrating the consistent strengthening of the policy of a strong statehood. As a result, the analysis of the work reflects in bright colors the socio-political will, the morality of the members of the Sahibkiran family, close and devoted people, children.

Historical novel-tetralogy relying on the internal laws of the genre, finding commonality in the form of ideas, reality, goals, it is possible to trace how this work about Timur literally became a "The Great Empire". This is manifested in the writer's reinterpretation of each character in the work. The most important factor determining the art and evolution of the historical novel is its artistic and aesthetic impact on the foundations of human spirituality and society, on the minds and hearts of people. After all, the national historical novel figuratively expresses the aesthetic ideal of the nation. The novel describes the influence of the historical process on consciousness, thinking, and the spiritual world of a person.

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